

Table 1. Mortality of *Lissorhoptrus brevirostris* adults caused by *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarrhizium anisopliae* fungi, Sur del Jibaro, Sancti Spiritus, Cuba, 1978.

Fungus and strain	Rice water weevil mortality (%) 20 days after infection	
	Female	Male
	Beauveria bassiana 24	92
Beauveria bassiana 32	99	92
Metarrhizium anisopliae 12	83	79
Metarrhizium anisopliae 4	61	51

Insecticide-resistant brown planthopper populations at the IRRRI farm

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Brown planthopper (BPH) may develop resistance to some insecticides applied repeatedly. This has occurred in Japan and Taiwan, China. We found insecticide-induced BPH mortality to be much lower for populations collected from the IRRRI research farm than for greenhouse colonies (see figure).

Chlorpyrifos + BPMC has been used at IRRRI since 1978, and acephate has been used since 1981. For 10 years BPH-susceptible cultivars usually received two granular and six foliar insecticide applications per season. Using such quantities of insecticide has undoubtedly hastened the development of insecticide-resistant BPH populations at the farm. □

drobacilin, and Dipel) controlled rice water weevil when applied to 35-day-old rice plants as a foliar spray at 0.6, 1.2, and 2.4 kg/ha.

When *Neoplectana* nematodes were broadcast on the water surface in the laboratory, adult mortality was 82% between 8 and 18 days after application. In another test, three dosages of the nematode were applied. Rice water weevil damage was lowest with 36 nematodes/ml water which caused 77% adult mortality (Table 2). When the same test was

Table 2. Mortality of rice water weevil adults caused by different rates of *Neoplectana* nematode, Havana, Cuba, 1981.

Dosage (nematodes/ml water)	Rice water weevil mortality (%)
3550	80
355	82
36	17

done on rice water weevil larvae, mortality ranged from 73 to 83% 12 to 15 days after application. □

Mortality (%) 48 h after caging

Comparative mortality of greenhouse insecticide-free populations (---) and field populations (—) collected from IRRRI farm in Apr–Jun 1982 when treated with foliar sprays at 0.75 kg ai/ha.

A new gall midge parasite in M. P., India

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Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason), a destructive rice pest in India, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Vietnam, and Indonesia, has a large natural enemy complex. *Platygaster oryzae* is a dominant egg-larval gregarious parasite of gall midge. *P. oryzae* parasitism in Madhya Pradesh was 14.3% in the summer rice crop in Apr and May 1977.

During 1980 wet season a hymenopterous grub was found feeding on the pupae of *O. oryzae*. Adults were identified as *Neanastatus gracillarius* Masi (Eupelmidae: Hymenoptera) (identified by Z. Bouček). This is the first record of the parasite on *O. oryzae* in Madhya Pradesh. □

Influence of planting time on rice leaf folder incidence

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Rice leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée is a serious rice pest in samba season (Jul-Aug to Dec-Jan) at Tirur. We studied the effect of planting time on LF incidence.

IR20 was planted in 10-m² field plots on 7 dates with 4 replications during 1981–82 at PES, Tirur. Insecticide was not used. Total leaves and LF-damaged leaves on 25 randomly selected hills from

each plot were counted 60 days after transplanting and damage percentage was calculated (see table).

Leaf damage was significantly lower

Effect of planting time on rice leaf folder incidence, 1981–82 samba, Tirur, India.

Planting date	Mean leaf damage ^a (%) 60 DT
05 Aug 1981	39.7
20 Aug 1981	39.3
05 Sep 1981	41.7
20 Sep 1981	08.5
05 Oct 1981	13.2
20 Oct 1981	15.3
05 Nov 1981	13.6
CD	5.8

^aDT = days after transplanting.

(below the 20% economic threshold level) on crops planted from 20 Sep to 5 Nov. The early crop (5 Aug to 5 Sep) had heavy LF damage because maximum tillering and early flowering coincided with peak LF population (Oct–Nov).

Natural enemies of rice insect pests in Chhatisgarh (M.P.), India

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Natural enemies substantially reduce insect pest populations in rice fields. We began an intensive rapid roving monitor-

Natural enemies of rice insect pests in Chhatisgarh (M. P.), India, 1980-82.

Natural enemy	Host	Abundance (no./10 sweeps)	Incidence
<i>Predators</i>			
MIRIDAE			
<i>Tytthus parviceps</i> (Reuter)	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	2-8	Scattered
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i> Reuter	-do-	5-15	Widespread
LAGAEIDAE			
<i>Geocoris ochropterus</i> Fieber	Mites (<i>Oligonychus</i> sp.)	1-5	Scattered
<i>Graptostethus servus</i> (Fabricius)	Host not determined	2-5	Scattered
NABIDAE			
<i>Tropiconabis capsiformis</i> Germer)	<i>Nephotettix</i> spp.	5-15	Widespread
REDUVIIDAE			
<i>Coranus spiniscutis</i> Reuter	Host not determined	1-5	Scattered
TETRAGNATHIDAE			
<i>Tetragnatha</i> spp.	Leaffolder and hopper	5-15	Widespread
THOMISIDAE			
<i>Thomisus cherapunjesus</i> Tikader	Host not determined	1-5	Scattered
STAPHYLINIDAE			
<i>Paederus fuscipes</i> Curtis	Nymphs of <i>Nephotettix</i> spp.	5-20	Widespread (more in summer)
COCCINELLIDAE			
<i>Scymnus (Pullus) victoris</i> Motschulsky	Aphid (undetermined)	2-8	Isolated
<i>Coccinella</i> sp.	-do-	Rare occurrence	Isolated
<i>Parasites</i>			
DRYINIDAE			
<i>Gonatopus</i> sp.	Nymphs of <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> <i>Sogatella furcifera</i> <i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	2-8	Sporadic
EUELMIDAE			
<i>Eupelmus</i> sp. (urozonus-group)	Stem borer	2-8	Sporadic
PTEROMALIDAE			
<i>Mesopolobus</i> sp.	Stem borer	2-10	Scattered
EULOPHIDAE			
<i>Tetrastichus schoenobii</i> Ferr.,	<i>Tryporyza incertulas</i>	Rare occurrence	Scattered
PLATYGASTERIDAE			
<i>Platygaster oryzae</i>	<i>Orseolia oryzae</i>	1-5 ^a	Scattered
BRACONIDAE			
<i>Apanteles</i> spp.	Stem borer	1-5 ^a	Isolated

^a Number/m².

ing of insects and their parasites, predators, and diseases in Chhatisgarh in 1980. An area 8,000 to 10,000 km² was covered and 900 to 1,200 paddy fields were surveyed annually during kharif. Several integrated pest management technology studies in farmer fields also provided data.

Most of the area surveyed was rainfed and no more than 150-200 g ai insecticide/ha was applied annually. Insecticides used by farmers were malathion, phosphamidon, carbaryl, and BHC. Varieties were 75% local and tall and 25% were the high yielding gall midge-resistant varieties Phalguna (R.P.W. 6-17), Surekha (W13400), Asha (R-35-2752), and Usha (R-35-2750), and popular varieties Kranti and Madhuri. The crop was 75-85% broadcast. Populations of beneficial insects were determined by the number of insects in 10 net sweeps or in 1-m² areas.

We found large populations of *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter, *Tropiconabis capsiformis* (Germer), *Gonatopus* sp., *Tetragnatha* spp., and *Paederus fuscipes* Curtis (see table). These parasites and predators can be useful tools to reduce populations of harmful insects. The names of possible hosts given in the table did occur with the beneficials and were listed as hosts based upon available literature. □

Cytology of *Nilaparvata bakeri* (Muir), a grass-infesting planthopper species

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A grass-infesting planthopper, *Nilaparvata bakeri* (Muir), was found on the common weed *Leersia hexandra* (Swartz) at IIRRI experimental farm. *L. hexandra* is a host of a distinct but nonrice-feeding *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) population. The two planthopper species could easily be distinguished by genitalic characters. Following is a description of *N. bakeri* cytology.

Different stages of the first meiotic division in *N. bakeri*. a = pachytene, b = diakinesis, c = prometaphase I, d = metaphase I, e = anaphase I, and f = telophase I. X-chromosomes are indicated by arrows. Magnification 1000 X. IIRRI, 1983.